

Prediction of overloaded concentration profiles under ultra-high-pressure liquid chromatographic conditions

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ABSTRACT

In this study, overloaded elution profiles under ultra-high-pressure liquid chromatographic (UHPLC) conditions and accounting for the severe pressure and temperature gradients generated, are compared with experimental data. The model system consisted of an C18 column packed with 1.7- μm particles (i.e., a UHPLC column) and the solute was 1,3,5-tri-tert-butylbenzene eluted with a mobile phase composed of 85/15 (v/v) acetonitrile/water. Two thermal modes were considered, and the solute was eluted at the very high inlet pressures necessary to achieve a highly efficient and rapid chromatographic process, as provided by using columns packed with small particles. However, the high inlet pressure and high linear velocity of the mobile phase caused the production of a significant amount of heat, and consequently, the formation of axial and radial temperature gradients. Due to these gradients, the retention and the mobile phase velocity were no longer constant. Thus, simple mathematical models consisting only of the mass balance equations are unsuitable to properly model the elution profiles. Here, the elution concentration profiles were predicted using a combined two-dimensional heat and mass transfer model, also including the calculation of the mobile phase velocity distribution. The isotherm adsorption model was the bi-Langmuir isotherm model with Henry constants that depended on the local temperature and pressure in the column. These adjustments allowed us to precisely account for changes in the shape and retention of the overloaded concentration profiles in the mobile phase. The proposed model provided accurate predictions of the overloaded concentration profiles, demonstrating good agreement with experimental profiles eluted under severe pressure and temperature gradients in the column even in the most extreme cases where the pressure drops reached 846 bar and the temperature gradients equaled 0.15 K mm⁻¹ and 0.95 K mm⁻¹ in the axial and the radial directions, respectively. In such cases 36 % decrease of the retention factor was observed along the column and 2 % increase in radial direction. These changes, combined with the velocity distribution, shifted the overloaded elution profile's shock towards the center of the column, advancing approximately 3 mm from its initial position close to the column wall. Ultimately, this resulted in the broadening of the elution band.

1. Introduction

Chromatographic separation using columns packed with sub-2- μm particles is known as ultra-high-pressure liquid chromatography (UHPLC) [1]. This kind of chromatography emerged from the trend of packing the column with increasingly small particles. Using finer particles advantageously decreases the mass transfer resistance (significantly improving the column efficiency), increases the optimal velocity, and decreases the column length, decreasing the analysis time. However, the major problem in UHPLC is the appearance of temperature gradients in the axial and radial directions as a result of heat generation

due to the percolation of the viscous fluid through the column bed at high velocity and high pressure. All temperature gradients influence a chromatographic separation. The consequences of these temperature distributions for the thermodynamic and kinetic properties of the chromatographic columns are well known. Numerous papers [2–9] present theoretical and experimental investigations of the effects of heat generation in chromatographic columns. Generally, the axial temperature gradient mainly influences the retention time while the radial temperature gradient mainly influences the column efficiency. The most undesirable gradient is therefore the radial temperature gradient, which can cause the peak to broaden or even become distorted [10].

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We have previously shown experimentally and numerically that one way to eliminate the radial temperature gradient is by using a column packed with a chromatographic bed having high thermal conductivity [11]. Theoretical investigation indicates that columns packed with a solid phase having a thermal conductivity higher than about $50 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ do not display the loss of efficiency of the typical mobile phase used in chromatography [12]. We used a Diamond FLARE column with particles having an effective thermal conductivity of $85 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, for which the calculated maximal radial gradient (i.e., temperature difference between the column center and its wall) was $0.022 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [11]. Moreover, for a column immersed in turbulently flowing water, it was found that such thermal control of the column wall greatly promotes the creation of a radial gradient [10]. In practice, this means that such a column does not exhibit any radial temperature distribution in the water-controlled temperature mode. However, the typical columns used in chromatography have a silica matrix, which is characterized by a thermal conductivity of $1.4 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$; the effective solid phase conductivity of such a column is lower due to the attached matrix carbon ligands. Thus, during realistic chromatographic separation using UHPLC, it is almost impossible to prevent the creation of axial and radial temperature gradients.

To simulate a UHPLC separation, two-dimensional mass and heat transfer models must be formulated. Moreover, suitable models for calculating the mobile phase velocity and pressure distribution are needed. In previous studies [10,13] we proposed such a model. It was based on a two-dimensional version of the equilibrium-dispersive model of mass balance: the heat transfer in the column bed and column wall was described with classical heat transfer equations, while the mobile phase velocity and pressure distribution were calculated using the iterative method [10]. This model has generally been successfully applied to predict analytical peaks in UHPLC [10,11] and analytical and overloaded elution profiles in supercritical fluid chromatography (SFC) [14–18]. With good accuracy, analytical peaks could be predicted even under extreme conditions in which the typical Gaussian peaks obtained in HPLC became trapezoidal in UHPLC due to thermal effects [10]. This mathematical model was also used to theoretically predict elution profiles in nonlinear chromatography under UHPLC conditions [19]. For a nonlinear isotherm and at low mobile phase flow rates, the elution bands have the classical triangular shape associated with the Langmuir isotherm model. However, at the highest considered mobile phase flow rates, the triangular elution bands were deformed. The shock of the Langmuir profile disappeared with an increasing mobile phase flow rate, due to the creation of a radial temperature gradient. Nevertheless, no systematic studies have investigated this phenomenon in detail or even utilized real experimental elution bands in calibrating and validating the mathematical model.

This study aims at predicting overloaded concentration profiles eluted at high pressure (e.g., in UHPLC) in columns that are temperature controlled using both the classical column-oven and turbulent water-bath modes. The prediction will take into account changes in the physicochemical properties of the mobile phase in both the axial and radial directions. To achieve this, a two-dimensional equilibrium-dispersive model, connected with a heat transfer model similar to the one presented by Kaczmarek [10], will be utilized to calculate the overloaded concentration profiles. In contrast to the previous model, a new method for calculating the pressure, velocity, and temperature distributions proposed in [20] will be introduced. For the first time this model will here be validated on the base of experimental data including the radial and axial temperature gradients in the column. The validity of this method will be confirmed by comparing it with experimental data obtained from a column operating up to 900 bar. Moreover, unlike Kaczmarek et al.'s previous [10] study, were only analytical profiles were examined, this investigation focus on overloaded elution profiles. For this purpose, an adsorption isotherm that depends on pressure and temperature must be proposed. Additionally, these models will be used to investigate the influence of radial temperature gradients on the

elution profile shape. Furthermore, eluent profiles resulting from the organic solvent modifier gradient elution will be presented and discussed using the same column operating up to 900 bar.

2. Mathematical model

Properly modeling concentration elution profiles at high pressure requires the use of a mathematical model consisting of three different models: (i) a heat transfer model (Section 2.1), (ii) a mass transfer model (Section 2.2), and (iii) a momentum transfer model (Section 2.3). The momentum transfer model, coupled with the continuity equation and the relationship between pressure and density, allows for the calculation of the velocity distribution of the mobile phase in the chromatographic column. The model used here is similar to the models previously presented in [10,13,20], but not identical. To avoid misunderstanding all equations of the model are presented.

2.1. Heat transfer model

It is assumed that the chromatographic column consists of a tube filled with packing. The internal radius of the tube is denoted by R_{int} (m), the external radius by R_{ext} (m), and the length of the column by L (m). The heat balance equations for the column bed, Eq. (1), and the column wall, Eq. (2), in cylindrical coordinates can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} (\varepsilon_i C_{p,m} + (1 - \varepsilon_i) C_{p,s}) \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - \varepsilon_i T \alpha \frac{\partial P}{\partial t} = & -C_{p,m} u_x \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} - C_{p,m} u_r \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \\ & + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \lambda_{\text{eff}} \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\lambda_{\text{eff}} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) \\ & - u_x (1 - \alpha T) \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} - u_r (1 - \alpha T) \frac{\partial P}{\partial r} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

and

$$C_{p,w} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\lambda_w}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) + \lambda_w \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2}, \quad (2)$$

where $C_{p,m}$, $C_{p,s}$, and $C_{p,w}$ are the mobile phase, stationary phase, and column wall heat capacity ($\text{J m}^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$), respectively. The coefficient ε_i is the total porosity, α is the mobile phase thermal expansion coefficient (K^{-1}), u_x is the mobile phase superficial velocity in the axial direction (x) (m s^{-1}), and u_r is the mobile phase superficial velocity in the radial direction (r) (m s^{-1}). Moreover, λ_{eff} is the effective bed conductivity ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$), λ_w is the column wall thermal conductivity ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$), P is the local pressure (Pa), and T is the local temperature (K).

The balance Eqs. (1) and (2) have to be coupled with the following initial and boundary conditions:

$$\text{for } t = 0 \quad T(x, r) = T_0. \quad (3)$$

At $r = R_{\text{ext}}$, the following conditions are assumed:

$$\text{for } t > 0, r = R_{\text{ext}} \quad -\lambda_w \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} = h_{\text{ext}} (T - T_{\text{ext}}), \quad (4)$$

$$\text{for } t > 0, R_{\text{int}} > r > R_{\text{ext}}, x = 0 \quad \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = 0, \quad (5)$$

and

$$\text{for } t > 0, R_{\text{int}} > r > R_{\text{ext}}, x = L \quad \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = 0. \quad (6)$$

where h_{ext} is the external heat transfer coefficient ($\text{W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$) and T_{ext} is the temperature of the fluid surrounding the column.

Regarding Eqs. (5) and (6), the column is connected to the pump and detector via steel end fittings. The end fittings overlap part of the external column walls and are connected to the annular part of the wall

between R_{int} and R_{ext} . The end fittings have complex shapes that will affect the temperature distribution [10,13,21].

At the boundary between the column packing and the column wall, the conditions of temperature continuity and heat flux continuity are required:

$$\text{for } t > 0, r = R_{\text{int}} \quad \lambda_w \frac{\partial T(r = R_{\text{int}}^+)}{\partial r} = \lambda_{\text{eff}} \frac{\partial T(r = R_{\text{int}}^-)}{\partial r} \quad (7)$$

and

$$T(r = R_{\text{int}}^+) = T(r = R_{\text{int}}^-). \quad (8)$$

At the center of the column, a symmetry condition was applied:

$$\text{for } t > 0, r = 0 \quad \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} = 0. \quad (9)$$

At the inlet to the column bed, constant temperature T_{in} of the mobile phase was assumed:

$$\text{for } t > 0, x = 0, r < R_{\text{int}} \quad T(r, x = 0) = T_{\text{in}}, \quad (10)$$

while at the column bed outlet:

$$\text{for } t > 0, x = L, r < R_{\text{int}} \quad \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = 0, \quad (11)$$

The other parameters of the heat transport model were calculated as follows. The mobile phase thermal expansion coefficient was calculated from the following relationship:

$$\alpha = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial T}, \quad (12)$$

where ρ is the local density of the mobile phase.

The effective thermal conductivity of the chromatographic bed was calculated from the Zarichnyak correlation [22]:

$$\lambda_{\text{eff}} = \varepsilon_1^2 \lambda_{\text{elu}} + (1 - \varepsilon_1)^2 \lambda_s + 4\varepsilon_1(1 - \varepsilon_1) \frac{\lambda_{\text{elu}} \lambda_s}{\lambda_{\text{elu}} + \lambda_s}, \quad (13)$$

where λ_{elu} and λ_s are the heat conductivity of the eluent and the stationary phase, respectively. The heat conductivity of the eluent was calculated using the following equation [23]:

$$\lambda_{\text{elu}} = w_{\text{MeCN}} \lambda_{\text{MeCN}} + w_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \lambda_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + 0.72 w_{\text{MeCN}} w_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} (\lambda_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - \lambda_{\text{MeCN}}), \quad (14)$$

where λ_{MeCN} and $\lambda_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ are the heat conductivity of the acetonitrile and water while w_{MeCN} and $w_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ are the mass fraction of the acetonitrile and water, respectively.

2.2. Mass transfer model

The equilibrium-dispersive (ED) model was used to describe the mass balance over the column. The two-dimensional ED model in cylindrical coordinates is expressed as:

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} + \frac{(1 - \varepsilon_1)}{\varepsilon_1} \frac{\partial q}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{\varepsilon_1} \text{div}(c \cdot \mathbf{u}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(D_{\text{ax}} \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r D_{\text{ar}} \frac{\partial c}{\partial r} \right), \quad (15)$$

where c and q are the solute concentrations (g L^{-1}) in the mobile and stationary phases, respectively, D_{ax} and D_{ar} are the apparent dispersive coefficients ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$) in the axial and radial directions, respectively, and \mathbf{u} is a vector of the mobile phase velocity.

The apparent axial dispersion coefficient, $D_{\text{a,x}}$, was calculated using the following equation [24]:

$$D_{\text{a,x}} = \frac{D_L \varepsilon_c}{\varepsilon_1} + \left(\frac{k_1}{1 + k_1} \right)^2 \frac{u^2 d_p}{6\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_c F_c} \left(\frac{\tau d_p}{10\varepsilon_c D_m} + \frac{1}{k_{\text{ext}}} \right), \quad (16)$$

where

$$k_1 = F_c \left(\varepsilon_p + (1 - \varepsilon_p) \frac{\partial q}{\partial c} \right) \quad (17)$$

and

$$F_c = \frac{1 - \varepsilon_c}{\varepsilon_c}, \quad (18)$$

where D_L is the local dispersion coefficient ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$), D_m is the molecular diffusion coefficient ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$), k_{ext} is the external mass transfer coefficient (m s^{-1}), d_p is the particle diameter (m), and τ is the tortuosity coefficient.

The radial dispersion coefficient, $D_{\text{a,r}}$, was calculated from the equation derived by Knox [25]:

$$D_{\text{a,r}} = \frac{0.03 d_p u_x}{\varepsilon_1} + 0.7 D_m. \quad (19)$$

The molecular diffusion coefficient, D_m , was estimated using the Wilke–Chang equation [23]:

$$D_m = 7.4 \cdot 10^{-12} \frac{(\phi M)^{0.5} T}{\eta V^{0.6}} \quad (20)$$

where V is the molar volume of a solute at normal boiling point ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$), M is the molar mass of the solvent (g cm^{-3}), and ϕ is the association coefficient.

The external mass transfer coefficient, k_{ext} , was calculated from the Wilson–Geankoplis correlation [26]:

$$Sh = \frac{1.09}{\varepsilon_c} Re^{0.33} Sc^{0.33}, \quad (21)$$

where Sh , Re , and Sc are the Sherwood, Reynolds, and Schmidt numbers, respectively.

The tortuosity coefficient was calculated from the following correlation [27]:

$$\tau = \varepsilon_p + 1.5(1 - \varepsilon_p). \quad (22)$$

The dispersion coefficient, D_L , was calculated from the Chung and Wen relationship (Eq. (23)) [28] or from the Gunn correlation [29] (Eq. (24)):

$$\frac{\varepsilon_c D_L}{u_x L} = \frac{\varepsilon_c d_p}{L} \frac{1}{0.2 + 0.011 Re^{0.48}} \quad (23)$$

or

$$\frac{\varepsilon_c D_L}{u_x L} = B(1 + \sigma_v^2) + \frac{\sigma_v^2}{2} + \frac{\varepsilon_c}{\tau Re Sc}, \quad (24)$$

where

$$B = \frac{Re Sc}{4\alpha_1^2(1 - \varepsilon_c)}(1 - p)^2 + \frac{(Re Sc)^2}{16\alpha_1^4(1 - \varepsilon_c)^2} p(1 - p)^3 \left[\exp\left(\frac{-4\alpha_1^2(1 - \varepsilon_c)}{p(1 - p)Re Sc} \right) - 1 \right], \quad (25)$$

where α_1 is the first root of the zero-order Bessel function while σ_v is the dimensionless variance of the local velocity distribution in relation to the average velocity of the eluent.

The parameter p is calculated from the following equation:

$$p = 0.17 + 0.33 \exp\left(\frac{-24}{Re} \right), \quad (26)$$

The physicochemical properties of the eluent were taken from REFPROP [30].

The ED model must be connected with the appropriate isotherm equation. Here we applied the classical bi-Langmuir isotherm model:

$$q = \frac{H_1 c}{1 + H_1 c/q_{s0,1}} + \frac{H_2 c}{1 + H_2 c/q_{s0,2}}, \quad (27)$$

where H_i is the Henry constant while $q_{s0,i}$ is the saturation capacity (L g^{-1}) for i th adsorption site and $P \rightarrow 0$. The influence of local temperature and pressure on the concentration solute in the stationary phase was taken into account by introducing the following equation for calculating the Henry constants [31]:

$$H(T, P) = H_0 \exp\left(\frac{-E}{RT}\right) \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta VP}{RT}\right), \quad (28)$$

where E is the activation energy of adsorption (J mol^{-1}), R is the universal gas constant ($\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$), and ΔV is the difference between the partial molar volumes of the solute in the adsorbed layer and the liquid phase ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$). In the case of the bi-Langmuir isotherm model, the Henry constant is the sum of two terms related to the two different adsorption sites:

$$H = H_1 + H_2. \quad (29)$$

It was assumed that the temperature and pressure dependencies in Eq. (28) are the same for the two kinds of adsorption sites and that only the pre-exponential parameters are responsible for the different values of these two Henry constants:

$$H_1 = (H_0 - H_{0,2}) \exp\left(\frac{-E}{RT}\right) \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta VP}{RT}\right) \quad (30)$$

and

$$H_2 = H_{0,2} \exp\left(\frac{-E}{RT}\right) \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta VP}{RT}\right). \quad (31)$$

The mass transfer model was solved assuming a rectangular inlet concentration impulse and Danckwerts boundary conditions [27]. Namely,

$$\text{for } t > 0, x = 0 \quad u[c_F - c] = \varepsilon_t D_a \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} \quad (32)$$

and

$$c_F = \begin{cases} c_0, & t \in [0, t_{inj}] \\ 0, & t > t_{inj} \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

$$\text{for } t > 0, x = L \quad \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (34)$$

where c_0 (g L^{-1}) and t_{inj} (s) are the concentration of the solute injected at the inlet of the column and the time of the solute injection, respectively. Another boundary conditions needed for the solving Eq. (15) are defined in the following way:

$$\text{for } t > 0, r = 0 \quad \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (35)$$

$$\text{for } t > 0, r = R_{int} \quad \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (36)$$

The initial boundary conditions are following:

$$\text{For } t = 0 \quad c(x, r) = 0 \text{ and } q(x, r) = 0 \quad (37)$$

2.3. Momentum transfer model

In the most advanced modeling, the velocity distribution is obtained by solving the Navier–Stokes equation for fluid percolating through a packed bed together with heat and mass transfer [21]. The disadvantage of using this model is the very long computation time.

However, in the case of the chromatographic column, it is commonly accepted that the relationship between the flow rate and pressure drop

describes Darcy's law:

$$\mathbf{u} = -\frac{\kappa}{\eta} \text{grad}(P). \quad (38)$$

This assumption simplifies the model and enables its faster solution; the local pressure was calculated based on the continuity equation (Eq. (39)) using the method proposed in [20]:

$$\varepsilon_t \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} - \text{div}(\rho \cdot \mathbf{u}) = 0. \quad (39)$$

Incorporating Eqs. (38) into (39) gives the following equation:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{\varepsilon_t} \text{div}\left(\rho \cdot \frac{\kappa}{\eta} \text{grad}(P)\right). \quad (40)$$

In the above equations, ρ is the local fluid density (kg m^{-3}), \mathbf{u} is the mobile phase superficial velocity vector (m s^{-1}), κ is the bed permeability coefficient (m^2), and η is the local fluid dynamic viscosity (Pa s).

Density depends on time, pressure, and temperature, so the unknown $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t}$ can be found by using the chain rule:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial P} \frac{\partial P}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial T} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t}. \quad (41)$$

Eq. (40) can be rewritten in the form:

$$\varepsilon_t \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial P} \frac{\partial P}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial T} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \right) - \text{div}\left(\rho \cdot \frac{\kappa}{\eta} \text{grad}(P)\right) = 0. \quad (42)$$

Eq. (42) can be solved numerically with the initial condition:

$$\text{for } t = 0 \quad P = P_0 \quad (43)$$

and the boundary conditions:

$$\text{for } t > 0, r = R_{int} \quad \frac{\partial P}{\partial r} = 0 \quad (44)$$

and

$$\text{for } t > 0, r = 0 \quad \frac{\partial P}{\partial r} = 0. \quad (45)$$

Assuming constant mass flow rate in any cross-section of a column, even at a column inlet denoted by the 0 index:

$$(u_x \rho)_{\text{average}} = \text{const} = u_{x0} \rho_0 = -\rho_0 \frac{\kappa}{\eta} \frac{dP}{dx}, \quad (46)$$

the boundary condition at the column inlet can be obtained:

$$\text{for } t > 0, x = 0 \quad u_{x0} \rho_0 = -\rho_0 \frac{\kappa}{\eta_0} \frac{dP}{dx} \Big|_{x=0}. \quad (47)$$

Another boundary condition is the constant pressure, P_{out} , at the column outlet:

$$\text{for } t > 0, x = L \quad P = P_{\text{out}}. \quad (48)$$

The bed permeability coefficient is calculated from the Bird et al. relationship [32]:

$$\kappa = \frac{d_p^2 \varepsilon_c^3}{150(1 - \varepsilon_c)^2}. \quad (49)$$

The model presented in this section enabled us to successfully predict the retention time and peak width in temperature gradient chromatography [20].

The mathematical model is also presented in the form of a simplified sketch, see Fig. S1 in Supplementary materials.

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Chemicals and column

The mobile phase consisted of gradient-grade acetonitrile (MeCN) (Fisher Scientific, Loughborough, UK) and deionized water with a resistivity of 18.8 M Ω cm delivered by a Milli-QPlus 185 water purification system (Merck Millipore, Darmstadt, Germany). As a solute, 1,3,5-tri-tert-butylbenzene was used (Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA). For the gradient mode chromatography, 10-mer deoxythymidine monophosphate with the sequence 5'-TTTTTTTTTT-3' was used; here it will be called T10. The mobile phase additive for the T10 elution was dibutylammonium acetate (DBuAA), which was prepared by mixing equal amounts of dibutylamine (≥ 99.5 %, CAS number: 11-92-2) with acetic acid (≥ 99.5 %, CAS number: 64-19-7). For the pycnometry measurements, dichloromethane (Pro-labo Normapure; VWR International, Radnor, PA, USA) and MeCN were used.

The UHPLC column was a 100 \times 2.1-mm Acquity UPLC BEH C18 (Waters, Milford, MA, USA) with an average particle diameter of 1.7 μ m and a pore size of 138 Å; the surface area was 183 m² g⁻¹ and the total carbon content 17.4 %. The column hold-up volume was determined with a pycnometry method [33] using dichloromethane and acetonitrile. The determination of the total porosity was also checked using a non-retained marker (uracil). Detailed information about the column is found in Table S1, see Supplementary materials.

3.2. Instrumentation

Experiments were performed on an Acquity H-Class Bio System (Waters, Milford, MA, USA) with a quaternary solvent manager, an autosampler with a 50- μ L flow through a needle, a still-air column oven equipped with a mobile phase pre-heater, and a PDA detector with a 500-nL flow cell. The extra column volume from the autosampler to the detector was 29 μ L and has been subtracted from all experimental data. The influence of the extra column volume on the elution band broadening was neglected. The temperature of the column was controlled in two ways using either the air-controlled temperature mode described above or the stirred water-controlled temperature mode. In the stirred water-controlled temperature mode, the column was immersed in an aquarium containing turbulent water whose temperature was controlled with a thermostat.

The total mass flow of the mobile phase was measured after the detector by connecting a mini CORI-FLOW Coriolis mass flow meter (accuracy ± 0.2 %) (Bronkhorst High-Tech B.V., Ruurlo, Netherlands). The temperature of the column wall was measured using an attached PT-100 resistance temperature detector (Pentronic AB, Gunnebo, Sweden). The temperature signals were logged using a PT-104 data logger (Pico Technology, St. Neots, UK).

3.3. Procedure

The mobile phase was 85/15 (v/v) MeCN/water and the solute was 1,3,5-tri-tert-butylbenzene. The solute was dissolved in the mobile phase at concentrations of 0.01 g L⁻¹ and of 0.5 g L⁻¹, 1 g L⁻¹, 2 g L⁻¹, and 4 g L⁻¹ for the analytical and overloaded studies, respectively. In all cases, the injection volume was 10 μ L. Four different column loads were utilized for determining the calibration curve for each thermal mode and mobile phase flow rate considered in this study. The calibration curves were described by polynomial equations with linear and quadratic terms. The signal was recorded at 210 and 250 nm in the analytical and overloaded injections, respectively. The repeatability was checked using two injections. The column was operated in two different thermal modes: the air-controlled temperature mode with still air and the water-controlled temperature mode with turbulent water flow. The temperature of the still air and the stirred water was 25.0 \pm 0.1 °C. In both cases, the pre-heater was operating and the temperature was set at 25.0 °C. In

the still-air mode, the temperature of the column wall was measured at three points by attaching three temperature sensors 2.0 cm, 5.0 cm, and 8.0 cm from the column inlet using a thermal adhesive from Arctic Silver Inc. (Visalia, CA, USA); the PT-100 temperature sensors used measured the temperature with an accuracy of ± 0.2 °C. The pressure at the column inlet and outlet was determined by repeating the experiments first with the capillary going to the column inlet reconnected directly to waste and then with the column replaced with a zero-volume connector. The elution profiles were recorded at mobile phase flow rates ranging from 0.05 to 0.9 mL min⁻¹. The mobile phase flow rate was increased from 0.1 mL min⁻¹ to 0.9 mL min⁻¹ in increments of 0.1 mL min⁻¹.

In the gradient experiments, two different mobile phase flow rates were considered: 0.1 mL min⁻¹ and 0.45 mL min⁻¹. The highest flow rate was limited by the maximum system pressure of the instrument, i.e., 1034 bar. In the gradient experiments, the MeCN gradient increased from 19.9 % to 27.7 % [v/v] over 60 min and 13.33 min at mobile phase flow rates of 0.1 mL min⁻¹ and 0.45 mL min⁻¹, respectively. The isocratic hold in the gradient program was 3.46 min and 0.77 min at mobile phase flow rates of 0.1 mL min⁻¹ and 0.45 mL min⁻¹, respectively. The isocratic hold and the gradient times were scaled to the applied mobile phase flow rate such that in both considered cases the gradient slope was 1.3 % mL⁻¹. The DBuAA concentration was constant at 60 mM. The experiment was conducted at a temperature of 25 °C. The injection volume was 10 μ L with the sample containing 0.5 g L⁻¹, 2 g L⁻¹, and 4 g L⁻¹ of T10.

3.4. Calculation

The mathematical model was solved using the method of orthogonal collocation on finite elements (OCFE) [34]. The OCFE method was selected because it has been proven to be a most reliable calculation method among several tested, see section 10.4.2 in reference [27] for more details. The set of ordinal differential equations obtained after discretizing the spatial derivatives was solved using the CVODE solver available in the SUNDIALS package [35]. CVODE was selected because the SUNDIALS package is well-known for its high performance and is regarded as one of the best ODE solvers; recently it was even recognized as an award-winning computational tool [36]. The BDF method implemented in CVODE were used. The unknown model parameters were estimated using the Levenberg–Marquardt procedure [37]. In the inverse method, the parameters were estimated by minimizing the sum of squared differences between the experimental and calculated values. The precision of the determination of the model parameters was calculated based on the formulas given by Seber [38] for the 95 % confidence interval of Student's *t*-test. The accuracy, correctness, and CPU time of computations are discussed in more detail in Section 1.3 in the Supplementary materials.

To properly calculate the concentration profile in UHPLC, the temperature and pressure distributions in the column must first be calculated using the heat and pressure transfer models (see Sections 2.1 and 2.3). The unknown parameters of the heat and pressure transfer models are the external heat transfer coefficient, solid phase conductivity, and external porosity. The external heat transfer coefficient is used in the boundary condition in Eq. (4) and captures the heat transfer between the column wall and surrounding air. The effective solid phase conductivity captures the heat conductivity of the silica matrix covered by octadecyl ligands. The external porosity is mainly responsible for the pressure drop and was calculated using the model that links the local pressure with the mobile phase velocity (see Section 2.3). These parameters were estimated based on the determined inlet pressure and on temperatures measured 2 cm, 5 cm, and 8 cm from the column inlet at a mobile phase flow rate of 0.9 mL min⁻¹ in a column operating in air-controlled temperature mode. In this condition, the greatest changes in the mobile phase properties are expected.

The adsorption isotherm model parameters for calculating the overloaded elution profiles were estimated in two steps (see Eqs. (27)–(31)). First, the analytical mode was considered and unknown

parameters of the Henry constant (see Eq. (28)) were estimated based on three retention times. These retention times were chosen for a column operating in air-controlled temperature mode at mobile phase flow rates of 0.05 mL min^{-1} and 0.9 mL min^{-1} , and for a column operating in water-controlled temperature mode at a mobile phase flow rate of 0.8 mL min^{-1} . In the second step, the saturation capacities of the bi-Langmuir isotherm model (see Eq. (27)) and the pre-exponential parameter from Eqs. (30) and (31) were estimated based on an overloaded concentration profile obtained for a column operating in air-controlled temperature mode at a mobile phase flow rate of 0.05 mL min^{-1} . To estimate these parameters, an elution profile recorded for a sample concentration of 4 g L^{-1} was used. The values of all model parameters and auxiliary parameters used in the correlations are summarized in Table S1, see Supplementary materials.

When the concentration profiles were calculated, first the steady-state axial and radial temperature gradients were calculated as a function of the physicochemical properties of the mobile phase. Then the mass transfer model was solved using the calculated temperature and pressure distributions in the column. The detailed information regarding the code validation, method of the model solution and time of the computation is in Supplementary material, see Method of solution of the mathematical model defined in the article.

4. Results and discussion

The main aim of this study was to numerically model overloaded elution profiles under severe pressure and temperature gradients. This was accomplished through several steps, as outlined below. In Section 4.1, the heat and the new momentum transfer models are calibrated and validated, and detailed temperature and pressure distributions are presented. In Section 4.2, the influence of the temperature and pressure distributions on the properties of the mobile phase is presented and discussed. Section 4.3 presents the predicted overloaded concentration profiles using the two-dimensional ED model. In Section 4.4, the isocratic and gradient modes are compared.

4.1. Temperature and pressure distributions

To accurately calculate elution profiles under severe temperature and pressure gradients, the heat balance equations connected with the model calculating the velocity and pressure distributions inside the column must be considered. However, before that, some unknown model parameters must be determined, such as the external porosity, thermal conductivity of the solid phase, and external heat transfer coefficient. These parameters were estimated based on experimental data obtained at the highest mobile phase flow rate and in the air-controlled temperature mode, as explained in Section 3.4. The determined external porosity was 0.379, the effective thermal conductivity of the solid phase was $0.978 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, and the external heat transfer coefficient was $12.7 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$. These values are typical of those found in chromatographic systems and under the applied heat transfer conditions [10,13,27,32].

The heat transfer model and the momentum transfer model, using determined parameter values, were validated by comparing the calculated temperatures 2 cm, 5 cm, and 8 cm from the column inlet, as well as the calculated pressure at the column inlet, with the corresponding experimental values. Only the air-controlled temperature mode was used for comparing the calculated and measured temperatures, and the relative error of these calculations was no more than 0.1 % (see Table S4, Supplementary material). The greatest disagreement was 0.4 K, but in most cases, the difference was no greater than 0.2 K. This could be compared with the $\pm 0.2 \text{ K}$ accuracy of the temperature sensors. In the water-controlled temperature mode, it was assumed that there was no heat transfer resistance from the column wall to the surrounding water—in other words, the column wall temperature equaled the temperature of the surrounding water. The calculated pressures at the column inlet also agreed very well with the experimental values in both

temperature control modes (see Table S5, Supplementary material). In the air-controlled temperature mode, the greatest difference observed was 5.7 bar and the relative error did not exceed 7 %, although it was usually less than 1 %. In the water-controlled temperature mode, the greatest difference in the calculated pressure at the column inlet was 34.4 bar at the highest mobile phase flow rate, resulting in a 3.8 % relative error. This discrepancy in calculated pressures can be considered acceptable. Note that the external porosity was estimated using the data obtained in the air-controlled temperature mode. When this parameter was estimated using pressure determined in the water-controlled temperature mode, the agreement in the pressure calculations was very good in the water-controlled temperature mode but discrepancies were observed in the calculations for the air-controlled temperature mode. Moreover, these discrepancies were similar to those in the former case, i.e., when the pressure was calculated for the column kept in water. However, the difference between determinations of the external porosity in both cases was less than 1 %. It should be also mentioned that in these simulations we use the new model for the calculation of the velocity and the pressure distributions in the column, see Section 3.2. The obtained agreement between the experimental and the calculated value of temperature and inlet pressure completely confirmed the validity and usefulness the applied momentum transfer model in prediction of the pressure and velocity in the case radial and axial temperature gradients.

The validated heat transfer model connected with the momentum transfer model were used for calculating the temperature distribution at all mobile phase flow rates in both thermal modes. Fig. 1 shows the calculated temperature gradients over the column in the a) air-controlled temperature mode and b) water-controlled temperature mode at a flow rate of 0.8 mL min^{-1} (the highest flow rate in the water-controlled temperature mode). As can be seen, large radial or axial temperature gradients, depending on the thermal mode, are created due to the viscous heating. In the air-controlled temperature mode, the temperature difference between the column outlet and inlet is 13.2 K while the greatest radial temperature difference between column center and near its wall is 0.68 K, observed at the end of the column (see Fig. 1a). At a mobile phase flow rate of 0.9 mL min^{-1} (not presented here), these differences are 15.5 K and 0.8 K, respectively. The radial temperature difference increases from the column inlet to the outlet and is no greater than 0.5 K along almost the whole column length. Only in the first 5 mm of the column from the inlet are large radial temperature differences of about 1 K observed. Here, the observed temperature gradient has the opposite sign, because the eluent entering the column is colder than the column walls. In this instance, heat is transported mainly from the warmer column wall, resulting in the center of the column being the coldest and the temperature increasing in the radial direction from the center.

In contrast to the air-controlled temperature mode, in the water-controlled temperature mode, the axial gradients are much smaller, although larger radial gradients can be observed (see Fig. 1b). The radial temperature differences between the column center and near its wall are approximately 1 K along almost the entire column length. The main reason for these radial temperature gradients is the column walls, with have relatively high heat conductivity ($16 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$), being cooled by the surrounding turbulently flowing water. The presence of the column wall tends to homogenize the column temperature by transferring heat from the warmer outlet part of the column toward its cooler inlet and conveying the heat to the surrounding turbulent water. The magnitude of the temperature gradient depends on the intensity of the heat losses; the larger the radial heat losses, the larger the radial temperature gradient and smaller the axial temperature gradient. Therefore, in the water-controlled temperature mode we can observe large radial temperature distribution almost along the whole column length.

The temperature drop in the radial direction was calculated for a radius of 1.05 mm, while the axial temperature drop was calculated for a column length of 100 mm. Inspecting the temperature gradient per mm,

Fig. 1. Temperature distribution profiles (in Kelvin) in the (a) air-controlled temperature mode and (b) water-controlled temperature mode. The mobile phase flow rate is 0.8 mL min^{-1} , at which the pressure drops along the column are 729.8 bar and 845.5 bar in the air- and water-controlled temperature modes, respectively. Radius 0 is the center of the column, while the vertical dashed (in a, black; in b, white) line represents the inner column wall.

we can see that the radial gradient observed in the water-controlled temperature mode is around 0.95 K mm^{-1} , while the axial temperature gradient observed in the air-controlled temperature mode is 0.13 K mm^{-1} . This illustrates how the steep radial temperature gradient is observed in the column working under water-controlled temperature mode (see above discussion concerning Fig. 1b).

4.2. Density, viscosity, and velocity distributions

The density and viscosity of the mobile phase vary with temperature and pressure. As discussed in Section 4.1, when the separation system operates at high flow rates, large temperature and pressure gradients occur in both the axial and radial directions. Consequently, there are viscosity and density gradients inside the column. Since the mobile phase velocity depends on both viscosity and pressure, as shown in Eq. (38), this causes velocity gradients in the radial and axial directions.

Fig. 2 shows the calculated local a) density and b) viscosity values along the column at a mobile phase flow rate of 0.8 mL min^{-1} and at radius of 0 mm (dashed lines) and 1.05 mm (solid lines). The upper red lines show the changes calculated for the water-controlled temperature mode, while the lower black lines show changes for the air-controlled temperature mode. Both the density and viscosity of the mobile phase decrease along the column due to temperature and pressure changes. At the same mobile phase flow rate, the calculated density and viscosity in the water-controlled temperature mode are higher than in the air-controlled temperature mode. This is mainly because the average temperature is lower and the average pressure is higher in the water-controlled mode. However, the most important changes occur in the radial direction. The viscosity and density are higher near the column wall than in the center of the column. In the water-controlled temperature mode, the difference is greater, due to the increased radial temperature gradients observed along the column immersed in turbulently flowing water, compare Fig. 1a and b.

The changes in viscosity and pressure result in the velocity of the mobile phase no longer being constant, see Section 2.3. Fig. 3 shows the calculated local axial velocity for the a) air-controlled temperature mode

and b) water-controlled temperature mode. As can be seen, changes in the axial velocity are closely correlated with the temperature, pressure, viscosity, and density gradients. For the column whose temperature is controlled by natural convection, the mobile phase velocity is lower in the center of the column than near its wall in the first 5 mm of the length, due to the column wall being warmer than the column bed (see Fig. 1a). Beyond this distance, the velocity profile is almost flat, with only a slight parabolic tendency noted. In contrast, for the column whose temperature is controlled by turbulent water, a more parabolic flow profile is visible throughout the column (compare Figs. 3a and b), which will influence the overloaded elution bands.

4.3. Overloaded concentration profiles eluted under isocratic mode

Above, the temperature, pressure, density, and mobile phase velocity distributions in the column were calculated; here, they are used to calculate the overloaded elution profiles using a two-dimensional ED model. First, we need to select an appropriate adsorption isotherm model and determine its parameters. When the column is operating under very-high-pressure conditions, the isotherm model must include the local temperature and the local pressure inside the column.

The temperature and pressure dependencies of the adsorption isotherm (see Eq. (28)) were determined based on the analytical peaks obtained for the column operating in the air- and water-controlled temperature modes, as described in Section 3.4. The estimated parameters of the Henry constants are presented in Table 1. Fig. 4 shows the experimental (dotted blue lines) and simulated (solid black lines) analytical elution profiles for different mobile phase flow rates and the column operating in the a) air-controlled temperature mode and b) water-controlled temperature mode; the comparison for the other considered mobile phase flow rates is presented in Figs. S3a and b in the Supplementary material. The calculated retention times agree well with the experimental times, as shown in Table S6 in the Supplementary material. The maximum relative error does not exceed 1.2 %, which corresponds to a four-second difference between the calculated and experimental retention times. However, in most cases, the difference

Fig. 2. Calculated local (a) density (kg m^{-3}) and (b) viscosity (Pa s) of the mobile phase at different axial positions calculated in the water-controlled temperature mode (upper red lines) and air-controlled temperature mode (lower black lines). The dashed lines show the values at $R = 0$ mm (the center of the column), while the solid lines show the values at $R = 1.05$ mm (near the inner wall). The calculations were made for a mobile phase flow rate of 0.8 mL min^{-1} .

does not exceed 1 s.

As can be seen in Fig. 4a, the retention volume of the analytical peaks decreases with increasing mobile phase flow rate due to the increasing temperature in the column, as the adsorption process is exothermic. The opposite relationship is observed when the column is operating in the water-controlled temperature mode (see Fig. 4b), when the retention volume increases with increasing mobile phase flow rate. This indicates that even for small molecules, the pressure slightly increases the retention. Note that in this case, the average column temperature is almost independent of the mobile phase flow rate and that only the local pressure influences the retention [7].

4.3.1. Impact of column efficiency

The number of theoretical plates (N) was also estimated using the half-width method. The peak broadening expressed by N is caused by the radial temperature gradient, an axial dispersion, and internal and external mass transfer resistances. In this study, an attempt was made to model elution profiles using only the correlations to calculate the kinetic parameters, see Section 2.2. The effective diffusion coefficient and external mass transfer coefficient was calculated from the correlations commonly used in chromatography. The accuracy between calculated and experimental analytical peaks was checked by analyzing two known correlations for the calculation of the dispersion coefficient which were Gunn relationship (see Eq. (23)) and Chung and Wen relationship, see

Eq. (24). The results of these calculations are presented in Fig S4, where the van Deemter curves for the experimental and calculated elution profiles are plotted. Unfortunately, we have not found a correlation which gives better agreement than that from Fig. S4. Therefore, in the final calculations presented in Fig. 4 and Fig. S3, we used the Gunn correlation except for the mobile flow rates equal 0.05 mL min^{-1} , 0.1 mL min^{-1} and 0.2 mL min^{-1} for which the better prediction of the peak width gives Chung and Wen correlation. Similar results as here were also observed in [39, 40]. The final calculated and experimental values of the number of theoretical plates are presented in Table S6. The relative error of the calculation of the number of theoretical plates is quite large, in most cases, around 20% (cf. Table S6). But, note that at this point any kinetic parameters were not estimated. The error equal almost 50% seems to be large; expressing retention in function of time as on Fig. S5 (Supplementary material) we can regard the agreement between the calculated and experimental peaks as acceptable. If a better agreement is requested the dispersion coefficient or other kinetic parameters must be estimated on the base experimental data.

This study examines overloaded elution profiles, not analytical size peaks. Overloaded band shapes are mainly governed by adsorption/desorption thermodynamic, with N between 10,000 and 20,000 see Table S6, minimal impact elution profiles. A chromatographic column having an N of 5000 plates creates almost identical overloaded elution profiles as if the column has 30,000 plates ($N = 30,000$), which is why the elution by characteristics points method, which is based on the ideal model (i.e. assuming N to be ∞) can be used to acquire adsorption isotherms on LC systems with limited column efficiency [27,41]. In Fig. 1 in the study by Ravald and Fornstedt, shows that elution profiles calculated using N as 2000 closely resemble those calculated using N as 30,000 [42]. Therefore, the kinetic parameters do not have a significant impact on the shape of the elution profiles in our study.

Figs S6 a-f show the comparison between the experimental and the calculated elution profiles obtained using Gunn as well as Chung and Wen correlations for the mobile flow rates equal 0.05 mL min^{-1} (a, c, e) and 0.8 mL min^{-1} (b, d, f) with a sample concentration 0.01 g L^{-1} (a, b), 0.5 g L^{-1} (c, d) and 4 g L^{-1} (e, f). The column is working under water-controlled temperature mode. As shown, for the analytical injections the method of the calculation of the dispersion coefficient has significant meaning, see Fig S6 a and b. In contrast to this, the overloaded elution profiles (discussed in details below) do not show the significant dependences of the shape from the value of the dispersion. The elution profiles calculated for the sample concentration equal 0.5 g L^{-1} (the lowest overloading of the column) show small influence of the axial dispersion, while for the sample concentration equal 4 g L^{-1} (the highest overloading of the column), the elution profiles calculated using Gunn and Chung and Wen correlations cover each other, compare Figs. S6 c and d with e and f. Therefore, even if the apparent dispersion coefficient is not perfectly estimated, it does not influence significantly on the shape of the calculated overloaded elution profiles.

When discussing the efficiency of the column, it is worth paying attention to different numbers of N for the air-controlled and water-controlled temperature modes depending on the mobile flow rate, see Table S6. For the mobile flow rate equals 0.05 mL min^{-1} , the experimental value of N is the same in both thermal modes. However, increasing the mobile flow rate to 0.3 mL min^{-1} causes that the column working under water-controlled temperature mode has higher efficiency than column working under air-controlled temperature mode. Above the mobile flow rate equal 0.3 mL min^{-1} , the relationship is changing. In this range, the explanation of the different column efficiency is obvious. The radial temperature gradient highly promoted in water-controlled temperature mode causes the peak broadening and finally the column efficiency drop. In low range of the mobile phase flow rate, the explanation of this issue is not so obvious. Probably the axial temperature gradient promoted in the air-controlled temperature mode causes differences in the speed of movement front of the peak (faster movement) and end of the peak (slower movement) and finally it results in the peak

Fig. 3. Axial velocity distribution (m s^{-1}) calculated for the (a) air-controlled temperature mode and (b) water-controlled temperature mode. The mobile phase flow rate is 0.8 mL min^{-1} . Radius 0 is the center of the column.

Table 1

Estimated parameters of the isotherm model (see Eqs. (27)–(31)).

Parameters	Value	95 % confidence interval of Student's <i>t</i> -test
E (J mol^{-1})	$-1.645 \cdot 10^4$	$9.886 \cdot 10^1$
ΔV ($\text{m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	$-6.094 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$1.483 \cdot 10^{-7}$
H_0	$1.050 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.193 \cdot 10^{-4}$
$q_{s0,1}$ (g L^{-1})	$1.607 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$8.421 \cdot 10^{-3}$
$q_{s0,2}$ (g L^{-1})	$7.273 \cdot 10^1$	$1.125 \cdot 10^2$
$H_{0,2}$	9.92910^{-3}	$1.195 \cdot 10^{-5}$

broadening. In water-controlled temperature mode in the low range of the mobile phase flow rate, the temperature in the axial direction is almost constant and the radial temperature gradient is small and it does not cause the peak broadening. Therefore, we observe interesting higher efficiency of the column in water-controlled temperature mode. The simulations show the same phenomenon but not as clear as the experiments. This observation still requires detailed research to understand better.

4.3.2. Thermodynamics and impact of temperature control

To calculate the overloaded elution profiles, the bi-Langmuir isotherm model (see Eq. (27)) was applied. The Henry constants (H) were obtained from the analytical peak data, as described above, and the saturation capacities ($q_{s0,1}$ and $q_{s0,2}$) and H_2 were estimated based on the overloaded concentration elution profiles obtained for the column operating in the air-controlled temperature mode and at a mobile phase flow rate of 0.05 mL min^{-1} (see Section 3.4 for more details). The estimated parameters of the bi-Langmuir isotherm model are presented in Table 1. Figs. 5 and 6 show overlapping chromatograms from the experimental (dotted blue lines) and calculated (solid black lines) elution profiles for $10\text{-}\mu\text{L}$ injections of sample at concentrations of 0.5 g L^{-1} , $1, 2 \text{ g L}^{-1}$, and 4 g L^{-1} at mobile phase flow rates of a) 0.1 mL min^{-1} , b) 0.3 mL min^{-1} , c) 0.6 mL min^{-1} , and d) 0.8 mL min^{-1} for a column operating in the air-controlled temperature mode (Fig. 5) and water-controlled temperature mode (Fig. 6). Comparisons at other mobile phase flow rates considered in this study are presented in Figs. S7 and S8 (see Supplementary material). The proposed model can predict

the overloaded concentration profiles well at all considered mobile phase flow rates and in both thermal modes. The shift of the simulated elution bands relative to the corresponding experimental bands is similar to that of the analytical peaks and follows directly from the accuracy of the determination of the Henry constant; see Eq. (28), as discussed above.

The shape of the elution profiles clearly indicates that there are two different adsorption sites, justifying the selection of the bi-Langmuir model. Testing the Langmuir model resulted in poor model fit (results not shown), due to the characteristic curvature of the diffusion part. Applying the bi-Langmuir isotherm model significantly improved the prediction. From the obtained bi-Langmuir isotherm model parameters, it follows that the stationary phase is characterized by two kinds of adsorption sites: i) a small number of high-energetic adsorption sites and ii) a large number of low-energetic adsorption sites. The saturation capacity was determined to be 0.1607 g L^{-1} for the first kind of site and 72.73 g L^{-1} for the second kind, indicating that more than 99 % of the adsorption comes from the second kind of site. The equilibrium constant is pressure and temperature dependent. Operating the separation system in the air-controlled temperature mode and at a mobile phase flow rate of 0.05 mL min^{-1} , the determined equilibrium constants at average pressure (38.1 bar) and temperature (298.2 K) were 47.46 L g^{-1} and $0.006030 \text{ L g}^{-1}$ for the high- and low-energetic adsorption sites, respectively. Increasing the flow rate to 0.9 mL min^{-1} under the same thermal conditions and at average pressure (469.9 bar) and temperature (308.5 K) decreased the equilibrium constants to 42.2 L g^{-1} and 0.00536 L g^{-1} for the high- and low-energetic adsorption sites, respectively. These changes can be attributed to the dependencies of the Henry constants on pressure and temperature.

Inspecting the shape of the overloaded elution profiles (Fig. 5) from the column operating in the air-controlled temperature mode reveals no deformation. However, the shape of the overloaded elution profiles from the column operating in the water-controlled temperature mode (Fig. 6) is deformed, especially at high flow rates, i.e., the shock of the elution profile starts deforming as the mobile phase flow rate increases (see Figs. 6 and S8). This distortion is clearly visible at the highest mobile phase flow rate in the form of a kind of fronting (see Fig. 6d), and this distortion increases with decreasing column load. The deformation of

Fig. 4. Comparison between the experimental (dotted blue lines) and simulated (solid black lines) analytical concentration profiles of 1,3,5-tri-tert-butylbenzene eluted from the column operating in the (a) air-controlled temperature mode and (b) water-controlled temperature mode. The mobile phase flow rate was 0.05 mL min⁻¹, 0.2 mL min⁻¹, 0.4 mL min⁻¹, 0.6 mL min⁻¹, and 0.8 mL min⁻¹ from right to left in the air-controlled temperature mode and from left to right in the water-controlled temperature mode.

the shock of the concentration elution bands increases with decreasing column load because of the self-sharpening effect due to the thermodynamic column overload [27].

Fig. 7 shows the calculated concentration profiles near the column outlet at a mobile phase flow rate of 0.8 mL min⁻¹ and a sample concentration of 0.5 g L⁻¹ in the a) air-controlled temperature mode and b) water-controlled temperature mode. In the air-controlled temperature mode, the concentration profile does not display radial dependency. However, in the water-controlled temperature mode, the concentration profile displays clear radial dependency. The reason for the creation of the concentration profile arc is the radial temperature gradient created in the water-controlled temperature mode (see Section 4.1). The differences between the retention coefficients of the solute, as well as between the mobile phase velocities in the core region and near the column wall, cause the elution profile to move faster in the core region of the column than near the column wall. This is due to the retention factor, which decreases with increasing temperature, while the velocity of the mobile phase increases with increasing temperature. As illustrated by the calculated results shown in Fig. 7b, the shock of the elution profile in the column's central region is approximately 3 mm ahead of the shock that is moving near the column wall. Due to these differences, the shock of the elution profile will become distorted.

4.4. Overloaded concentration profiles eluted under gradient mode

To investigate how the gradient of the organic modifier influences the elution profiles eluted at very high pressure and to compare this

gradient with the isocratic elution, the elution bands of homomeric oligonucleotide T10 were recorded at very high inlet pressure in a column operating in both the air- and water-controlled temperature modes.

Fig. 8 shows the experimental profiles of 1,3,5-tri-tert-butylbenzene eluted in isocratic mode (see Fig. 8a and b) and the elution bands of homomeric oligonucleotide T10 eluted in gradient mode (see Figs. 8c and d) in a column operating in the air-controlled temperature mode (solid black lines) and water-controlled temperature mode (dashed red lines). The mobile phase flow rates were a) 0.1 mL min⁻¹ and b) 0.8 mL min⁻¹ for 1,3,5-tri-tert-butylbenzene, while for T10 the mobile phase flow rates were c) 0.1 mL min⁻¹ and d) 0.45 mL min⁻¹.

In the isocratic mode, the applied thermal mode significantly influences the elution bands, i.e., both the retention and shape of the elution profiles. A detailed explanation of this phenomenon is presented in Sections 4.1–4.3. In contrast, in the case of elution with a gradient of acetonitrile, no significant differences can be observed. Only at a mobile phase flow rate of 0.45 mL min⁻¹ do the elution bands recorded in the water-controlled temperature mode have a slightly shorter elution time than do the bands recorded in the air-controlled temperature mode, due to increasing retention factor with increasing temperature.

It should be noted that the elution profiles presented in Fig. 8b were acquired at a mobile phase flow rate of 0.8 mL min⁻¹ with pressure drops along the column of 729.8 bar and 845.5 bar in the air- and water-controlled temperature modes, respectively. Meanwhile, the elution profiles of T10 presented in Fig. 8d were acquired at a mobile phase flow rate of 0.45 mL min⁻¹ with pressure drops of 743.2 bar and 874.4 bar in the air- and water-controlled modes, respectively. It should be also

Fig. 5. Comparison between experimental (dotted blue lines) and simulated (solid black lines) overloaded concentration profiles of 1,3,5-tri-tert-butylbenzene eluted from the column operating in the air-controlled temperature mode at mobile phase flow rates of (a) 0.1 mL min^{-1} , (b) 0.3 mL min^{-1} , (c) 0.6 mL min^{-1} , and (d) 0.8 mL min^{-1} . The injection volume was $10 \text{ }\mu\text{L}$ and the concentrations of the samples were 0.5 g L^{-1} , 1 g L^{-1} , 2 g L^{-1} , and 4 g L^{-1} .

noted that in isocratic experiments the mobile phase was 85/15 [v/v] MeCN/water while in the gradient experiments the pressure drops are measured for the mobile phase at the beginning of the gradient for which the composition of the mobile phase is 19.9/80.1 [v/v] MeCN/water. Therefore, completely different viscosities of the mobile phases will result in different pressure drops. The amount of heat generated in the column is proportional to the pressure drop and the superficial velocity of the mobile phase. Thus, due to the almost two-times-lower mobile phase velocity, the amount of heat generated in the column is significantly lower. However, in the isocratic mode, significant differences between the air- and water-controlled temperature modes can still be observed at mobile phase flow rates of 0.4 mL min^{-1} and 0.5 mL min^{-1} . Here, the pressure drops at a mobile phase flow rate of 0.4 mL min^{-1} are 356.5 bar and 448.9 bar and at 0.5 mL min^{-1} are 386.3 bar and 494.5 bar in the air- and water-controlled temperature modes, respectively.

The small influence of the heat generation in the column on the retention and shape of the elution bands is probably attributable to the mechanism of oligonucleotide elution in gradient mode. The molecules of the oligonucleotide are strongly adsorbed to the stationary phase immediately after they are introduced to the inlet of the column and they either do not move or move very slowly along the column. When the concentration of the acetonitrile reaches a certain level in the mobile phase, the affinity of these molecules for the stationary phase quickly changes and they are very slowly retained. The oligonucleotide

molecules are very quickly eluted out of the column. Therefore, the influence of the temperature distribution is of little importance for the shape and behavior of the elution bands. Here, the gradient of the organic modifier dominates and controls the chromatographic process.

To summarize, both isocratic and in gradient elution, it is better to keep the column at air-controlled temperature mode. In isocratic elution, this prevents a temperature difference that can reduce efficiency during analytical injection. In overloaded mode, it maintains the elution profiles' shape. In gradient mode, both thermal modes work similarly, but for practical reasons, it is good to keep the column in the instrument's thermostat.

5. Conclusion

In this study, the overloaded concentration profiles eluted with very large pressure drops over the column were predicted using combined two-dimensional heat and mass transfer models connected with the momentum transfer model, allowing us to calculate the pressure distribution and mobile phase velocity distribution. The process of adsorbing 1,3,5-tri-tert-butylbenzene was described using the bi-Langmuir isotherm model. The temperature and pressure dependencies of the adsorption were included in the adsorption isotherm. Thus, the influences of the temperature and pressure distributions in the column on the retention of the solute and on the movement of the

Fig. 6. As in Fig. 5 but with the column operating in the water-controlled temperature mode.

Fig. 7. Calculated solute concentration profiles inside the column when the apex has reached about 9.5 cm from the column inlet in the (a) air-controlled temperature mode and (b) water-controlled temperature mode. The mobile phase flow rate is 0.8 mL min⁻¹, the injection volume 10 μL, and the sample concentration 0.5 g L⁻¹.

Fig. 8. Experimental elution profiles of 1,3,5-tri-tert-butylbenzene (a and b) and homomeric oligonucleotide T10 (c and d) recorded for a column operating in air-controlled temperature mode (black solid lines) and water-controlled temperature mode (red dashed lines). The mobile phase flow rates were (a) 0.1 mL min^{-1} and (b) 0.8 mL min^{-1} for 1,3,5-tri-tert-butylbenzene and (c) 0.1 mL min^{-1} and (d) 0.45 mL min^{-1} for T10. The injection volume was $10 \mu\text{L}$ and the sample concentrations were 0.5 g L^{-1} , 2 g L^{-1} , and 4 g L^{-1} . The pressure drops along the column were (a) 80.6 bar, (b) 729.8 bar, (c) 184.7 bar, and (d) 743.2 bar in the air-controlled temperature mode and (a) 85.8 bar, (b) 845.5 bar, (c) 189.2 bar, and (d) 874.4 bar in the water-controlled temperature mode. Observe that the blue lines show the concentration of MeCN at the column outlet. The pressure drop for the gradient mode was determined for the composition of the mobile phase at the beginning of the gradient.

elution bands due to the velocity distribution were precisely taken into account.

The model was calibrated and validated using experimental data. The calculated temperature distribution and pressure along the column agreed well with the corresponding experimental values, with a maximum relative error of 0.2 % for the temperature and 6.7 % for the inlet pressure. The good agreement confirmed the validity of the new momentum transfer model, which was applied in this study for the first time to the column operating with radial and axial temperature gradients.

The temperature gradient observed in the column depended on the applied thermal mode. For example, at a mobile phase flow rate of 0.8 mL min^{-1} in the air-controlled temperature mode, the axial temperature gradient (i.e., difference between temperature at the outlet and inlet of the column) was 13.17 K and the radial temperature gradient (i.e., difference between temperature inside the column and near its wall) was around 0.4 K, resulting in a pressure drop of 729.8 bar and a retention factor drop from 9.9 to 6.3 (36 % decrease). In contrast, in the water-controlled temperature mode, the axial temperature difference was

0.99 K and the radial temperature difference was 1 K, resulting in a pressure drop of 845.5 bar and a retention drop from 10.1 to 8.1 (20 % decrease). Moreover, along almost the entire column length in the water-controlled temperature mode, the retention factor near the column wall was about 0.2 higher (2 % increase) than in the central region of the column. It should also be mentioned that in the water-controlled temperature mode, for the retention drop was mainly responsible the pressure gradient due to the more or less constant temperature. Moreover, both the eluted profile shape and the retention time were also influenced by the axial and radial distribution of the mobile phase velocity. In the air-controlled temperature mode, the mobile phase velocity increased along the column and was constant in the radial direction, while in the water-controlled temperature mode, there was a smaller increase in velocity along the column but a greater radial distribution. As a result of the radial temperature gradient, the overloaded elution band was distorted.

Thus, we showed that the applied methodology and mathematical model led to good agreement between theoretical and experimental results. The model allowed us to predict the overloaded concentration

profiles eluted from columns operating at very high pressure with severe temperature gradients. Moreover, the calculations clearly explained the phenomenon of the distortion of the overloaded elution profiles taking place in the column with a large radial temperature gradient.

We also showed that in gradient elution mode, the influence of heat generation in the chromatographic column on the retention and shape of elution bands is reduced, primarily because the effect of the organic modifier dominates over the temperature and pressure dependencies of the adsorption.

This study is the introduction to the studies which will focus on modeling the more challenging and practical chromatographic systems which are two and multi component overloaded chromatographic systems in modifier concentration mode.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Marek Leško: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Validation, Formal analysis, Resources, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Krzysztof Kaczmarski:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Supervision. **Jörgen Samuelsson:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Torgny Fornstedt:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.chroma.2024.464704](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2024.464704).

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